

Supplementary Materials for

**Dysregulation of synaptic transcripts underlies network abnormalities in ALS
patient-derived motor neurons**

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Fig. S1. Motor neuron networks derived from hiPSCs expressed the motor neuron-specific marker Islet-1, and neuronal markers MAP2 and NeuN. Example images from a healthy (left) and ALS network (right) at 18 DIV (A), 38 DIV (B) and 52 DIV (C). Scale bars: 100 μ m.

Fig. S2. Immunocytochemistry confirmed the presence of astrocytes in the neural networks with positive expression of GFAP, as well as expression of β III tubulin and the motor neuron-specific marker ChAT. Scale bars: 100 μ m.

Table S1. Overview of cell media components used for motor neuron differentiation. Adapted from [Nijssen et al. \(2019\)](#).

		Days 1-2	Days 3-9	Day 10	Days 11-12	Day 13 onward
Catalog number & supplier	Reagents					
31331028, Thermo Fisher	DMEM/F12 + GlutaMAX	50%	50%			
21103049, Thermo Fisher	Neurobasal	50%	50%	100%	100%	100%
17502048, Thermo Fisher	N2 (100X)	0.5X	0.5X			
17504044, Thermo Fisher	B27 (50X)	0.5X	0.5X	1X	1X	1X
15070063, Thermo Fisher	Penicillin/Streptomycin	1X	1X	1X	1X	1X
Y0503, Sigma-Aldrich	Y-27632	5 μ m		5 μ m		
1614, Tocris	SB-431542	40 μ m				
6053, Tocris	LDN-193189	200 nM				
SML1046, Sigma-Aldrich	CHIR-99021	3 μ m				
R2625, Sigma-Aldrich	All- <i>trans</i> retinoic acid		200 nM	200 nM		
4366, Tocris	SAG	500 nM	500 nM			
A4403, Sigma-Aldrich	L-Ascorbic acid	200 μ m				
2634, Tocris	DAPT			10 μ m	10 μ m	
450-10, Peprotech	GDNF			10 ng/mL	10 ng/mL	10 ng/mL
450-02, Peprotech	BDNF			10 ng/mL	10 ng/mL	10 ng/mL

Table S2. Overview of the number of neural networks included in network analysis for each group from 24 to 52 DIV.

DIV	24	28	32	36	38	40	42	44	46	48	50	52
ALS	3	8	14	14	14	16	16	15	15	15	14	14
Healthy control	4	12	19	22	23	24	24	24	24	24	24	24

Table S3. P-values from statistical comparisons of ALS vs. healthy control for the network parameters used in the MEA analysis. Welch's t-test or Mann-Whitney U-test were applied as appropriate. Significant values ($p < .05$) in bold.

Network parameter	Day	24	28	32	36	38	40	42	44	46	48	50	52
Firing rate [Hz]		0.80437	0.294137	0.54885	0.097001	0.651857	0.00014	0.000053	0.005196	0.006083	0.000112	0.000005	0.007619
Mean amplitude [mV]		0.000015	0.022888	0.166823	0.537623	0.598889	0.111536	0.042618	0.041427	0.004972	0.001469	0.000108	0.000204
Mean ISI [s]		0.80437	0.294137	0.54885	0.097001	0.835266	0.00014	0.000053	0.005196	0.013197	0.000112	0.000005	0.014544
Coherence index		0.000006	0.838066	0.041039	0.011969	0.000916	0.000023	0.000002	0.000095	0.000106	0.000018	0.000046	0.000388
Burst frequency [Hz]		3.951622e-08	0.204806	0.138733	0.635384	0.276289	0.000424	0.000035	0.039788	0.095917	0.001703	0.000544	0.31792
Mean burst duration [s]		3.852850e-08	0.068948	0.207292	0.794255	0.398645	0.00245	0.000016	0.001033	0.001256	0.000027	1.020522e-07	0.000252
Mean IBI [s]		0.014883	0.038932	0.079985	0.924448	0.797269	0.00309	0.001934	0.123835	0.045996	0.00024	0.030837	0.219197
Fraction of spikes in bursts		3.951622e-08	0.185997	0.114471	0.924448	0.282837	0.000121	8.803486e-08	0.008735	0.004972	0.000288	0.000012	0.00208